

THE CATEGORY OF INSENSITIVITY IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR SPECIFIC FEATURES IN ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. The words that a person uses in everyday life induce in his mind an idea of the world around him, of society, of man himself. The transfer of information about this objective reality is also expressed in more complex linguistic units, phraseological units. The use of phraseology gives speech liveliness and colorfulness. Frequently to achieve a certain speech effect of simple words is not enough. Love, mockery, irony, bitterness and your attitude to what is happening- all this can be expressed more emotionally and exactly.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological units, intensity, category.

The study of phraseology of different languages suggests their classification according to the most diverse criteria. There are classifications that are widespread in linguistics and one of these types is Phraseological units. Phraseological unit is a stable combination, the generalized integral meaning of which is partly related to the semantics of their components, used in figurative meaning "*Boil over*"- "*Бить ключом*"- "*Come to a standstill*"- "*Займу в тупик*"- "*Boshi berk ko'chaga kirib qolmoq*", "*Go with the flow*"- "*Плыть по течению*" - "*Oqim bo'yicha ketmoq*". The main objectives of investigating phraseological units is the semantic and formal characteristic of not the components that make it up, not the connections of the components, but the study of the phraseological unit itself as an integral unit that has a well-defined form, its specific content and its own characteristics of use in speech.

In the course of cognition of objective reality, a person tries to find and create a picture of the world that receives a reflection in the language. The components of a fragment of a general linguistic picture of the world are phraseological turns. Some of them are included in the microsystem of a measure of a real occurrence or attribute characteristic in an object as its property or ascribed to it. These are phraseological units whose semantics contain the seme "*intensity*". Intensity is a quality that can be figuratively taken by the adjectives "*intense*". Intensity of phraseological units is advisable to name as the measure of one or another force.

According to E.N. Sergeeva, the category of intensity is a study, which consistently distinguishes between objective and affective comparisons, analyzes in detail the tendency to hyperbolize the intensity of the attribute as an expression of a certain mood, subjective attitude to the expressed. The author also introduces the concept of the "*norm*" of the intensity of the attribute, without which it is impossible to talk about the category of intensity.

The category of intensity, its features and means of expression in language and speech have attracted the attention of many scientists in recent decades. Intensity as a complex and multifaceted linguistic phenomenon is determined by scientists in different ways: either very narrowly, reducing its essence to expressing a high degree of a concept, or in the broadest sense of the word, highlighting it as the most important function of intensity - improving the

effectiveness of the stated, enhancing its impressiveness. According to the definition of Sh. Balli, the term “intensity” should be understood as all differences that are reduced to the categories of quantity, quantity, value, strength, etc., regardless of whether it is a question of specific ideas or abstract ideas”.

Each concrete phraseological unit reveals its linguistic nature with certain functions in the description of the realities of the world and is formed mainly on the basis of an emotionally colored image-representation. Intensity, on the other hand, refers to the objective quantitative certainty of a sign (less than normal - norm - more than normal), reflects the subjective perception of the degree of manifestation of a symptom and serves as an enhanced effect. The sign of intensity expressed by the phraseological unit is a quantitative reflection of how expressive rises above the objective logical content. The intensity is associated not with any quantitative qualification of the phenomenon, but only with one that demonstrates a deviation from the “normal measure”, i.e. from the normative zone, and as a result, it is perceived by speakers differently from the usual phenomenon corresponding to a certain norm, or measure. The measure and degree of phraseological unit show that most of the phraseological units of contain a semantic component “completely, entirely, fully”:

* <i>(black) like coal</i>	Чёрный <u>как</u> уголь	* <i>Ko'mirday qora</i>
* <i>(quiet) like a mouse</i>	Тихий <u>как</u> мышь	* <i>Sichqonday tovushsiz</i>
* <i>(busy) as a bee</i>	Занятой <u>как</u> пчела	* <i>Asal ariday band</i>
* <i>(Round) as a barrel</i>	Толстый <u>как</u> бочка	* <i>Bochkaday(cho'chqa)semiz.</i>
* <i>(Black) as night</i>	Туча тучей	* <i>Tunday qora</i>

As we see, the statics of the sign's value is entrenched in the phrase-accompanying word, and phraseological units intensify the sign, increasing the degree of its manifestation. The meaning of the analyzed phraseological units includes the seme “very” indicating a large degree, that is, the sign stated in the accompanying word is taken in its most extreme manifestation, to the greatest extent. Most of the phraseological measures and degrees presented in our material are correlated with the adverb “very” and through it their meaning in the process is explained. The adverb “very” in this case fulfills the function of expressive-emotional expression of the degree, category of intensity of the attribute, and is the main dominant among those similar to it in meaning.

Phraseology with the value of the intensity of the action / condition, correlating with relevant basic ontological categories, not only call certain actions and conditions, and (first of all), reflect the subjective perception of their quantitative identification, and therefore perform the function of increased impact on the recipient.

<i>I have worked <u>like</u> a horse today.</i>	Я сегодня работал <u>как</u> лошадь.	<i>Bugun men eshshakday ishladim.</i>
<i>She eats <u>like</u> a bird</i>	Она ест <u>как</u> птичка клюёт.	<i>U chumchiqni chimchilashiday yeyabdi.</i>
<i>Karim lives <u>like</u> a king.</i>	Карим живет <u>как</u> барин	<i>Karim shoxday yashaydi</i>
<i>His words were clear <u>as</u> a day.</i>	Его слова были ясны <u>как</u> день.	<i>Uning so'zlari kunday ravshan edi.</i>

“I worked like a horse today”, in the presented example it’s tense, long work is expressed using phraseology worked like a horse, ext. “**Worked like a horse,**” in which labor intensity is associated with Horse, a symbol of hard working.

Comparison can occur according to one or several well-known signs or processes:

<i>White <u>as</u> snow</i>	<i>Белый <u>как</u> снег</i>	<i>Qorday oppoq</i>
<i>Dumb <u>like</u> a fish.</i>	<i>Нем <u>как</u> рыбы</i>	<i>Baliqday saqov</i>

The first component of adjective (adverbial) phraseological units is used in its main literal meaning and is represented in most cases by the name adjective (adverb), less often by participles. For example:

<i>As healthy <u>as</u> a bull</i>	<i>Здоров <u>как</u> бык</i>	<i>Otday bo’lmoq</i>
<i>White <u>as</u> a ghost</i>	<i>Бледный <u>как</u> смерть</i>	<i>Arvoxday oqargan</i>

In the semantic sense, the first place is occupied by adjectives that denote the physical and spiritual qualities of people, their external features, the designations of the various properties and qualities of objects and phenomena of the real world:

<i>Poor <u>as</u> a church mouse.</i>	<i>Бедный <u>как</u> церковная</i>	<i>Cherkov sichqoniday</i>
<i>Stubborn <u>as</u> a mule</i>	<i>мышь</i>	<i>qashshox.</i>
	<i>Упрямый <u>как</u> осёл</i>	<i>Eshshakday qaysar</i>

The second component is most often represented by a noun, which may have qualifier words. A large group is formed by stable comparisons calling representatives of living beings: *Slippery like an eel – Скользящий как угорь.* The names of plants, substances, the most diverse objects and phenomena of the real world are readily involved in the role of the object of comparison.

Summarizing the above, it should be emphasized that in the modern English Russian and Uzbek languages there is a relatively large number of different-structural phraseological units that convey the expressive and intensive meaning of a high degree of any attribute or action, namely, phraseological units, sentence-substantive phraseological units, paired word combinations and phraseological constructions, which are characterized by free lexical replacement of the core component or are realized due to verbs that hyperbolize with their meaning described phenomena that do not occur in reality.

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